

Antibiotic prescribing practice for pediatric respiratory tract infections in a tertiary care hospital in Iraq

Inas Rifaat Ibrahim¹

¹ Department of Pharmacology and Clinical Pharmacy, College of Pharmacy, Uruk University, Baghdad, Iraq

Corresponding author: Inas Rifaat Ibrahim (p hm.enas@yahoo.com)

Received 30 January 2026 ♦ Accepted 7 March 2026 ♦ Published 25 March 2026

Citation: Ibrahim IR, Karwi YG, Mousah HA, Majeed IA (2026) Antibiotic prescribing practice for pediatric respiratory tract infections in a tertiary care hospital in Iraq. *Pharmacia* 73: 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.73.e187052>

Abstract

Prescribing antibiotics for pediatric patients with respiratory tract infections (RTIs) remains poorly studied in many low- and middle-income countries. This study aims to evaluate the quality of antibiotic prescribing for in-hospital pediatric patients with RTIs, identify predictors of this practice, and evaluate patients' clinical outcomes. A cross-sectional study was conducted at Baghdad Medical City from September 2025 to January 2026. Pediatric inpatients were selected using consecutive sampling, and data were collected from their medical records. Antibiotics were prescribed in 81.0% of cases, mostly cephalosporins (43.8%) and penicillins (34.6%). The intravenous (IV) route of administration was prescribed in 84.0% of cases. Prescribing quality was moderate (mean = 6.12 + 1.24). Antibiotics were prescribed for viral infections in 29.5% of cases (59 out of 200 patients); weight-based dosing was not documented in 27.3% of cases; and 7.1% of cases had a microbiological test performed. A longer hospital stay ($\beta = -0.18, P < 0.001$) and the use of IV antibiotics ($\beta = -0.72, P = 0.004$) were the only independent variables associated with lower prescribing quality. Most pediatric patients (94.5%) achieved successful treatment, with few adverse events (1.0%) and readmissions (3.5%). Despite the positive short-term clinical outcomes, significant shortcomings in diagnostic and prescribing practices remain.

Keywords

Antibiotics, Iraq, pediatric, respiratory tract infections

Introduction

RTIs are one of the most common illnesses in children. Globally, they are among the leading causes of pediatric hospitalization (Nair et al. 2013). Lower respiratory infections like pneumonia remain a leading cause of illness and death in children, especially in low and middle-income countries (GBD 2016 Lower Respiratory Infections Collaborators 2018; World Health Organization 2024). Despite advancements in supportive care and vaccinations, respi-

ratory infections heavily affect children's health and result in the prescribing of unnecessary antibiotics. Although viruses account for a large share of these infections, antibiotics remain the most prescribed medications for children with respiratory symptoms. Studies across the globe have shown that antibiotics are overprescribed for RTIs in children, including prescribing them when not needed, prescribing broad-spectrum rather than narrow-spectrum antibiotics, and failing to reassess the need for antibiotics (Hersh et al. 2013; Havers et al. 2018). These factors lead

to increased antibiotic resistance, higher healthcare costs, longer hospital stays, and adverse side effects. Global studies conducted in hospital settings have shown high use of empiric broad-spectrum antibiotics, limited microbiological analysis, and low rates of de-escalation of therapy once clinical stability is achieved (Di Pietro et al. 2017; Donà et al. 2020). The most common explanations for this are a lack of guidelines, difficulties in diagnosing illnesses, the severity of illnesses, and a culture of excessive prescribing within the institution. However, adherence to guidelines for managing paediatric respiratory infections and how this is implemented across hospitals in Middle Eastern countries has not been well evaluated.

Antimicrobial stewardship programs (ASPs) aim to reduce antibiotic prescribing by improving selection, dosing, duration, and route of administration, using guidelines and other evidence-based interventions. These interventions include audits and feedback, clinical decision support, and cross-disciplinary collaboration. These programs have been successful in pediatric hospitals by balancing antibiotic use, avoiding patient safety lapses, and reducing the risk of treatment failure (Gerber et al. 2013; Nedved et al. 2023). However, there is significant variation in the intervention structure, absence of infectious disease specialists, formal audit systems, and clinical pharmacists, as well as a notable lack of stewardship.

Most studies conducted on the consumption of antibiotics in children have concentrated on quantifying prescriptions and antibiotic usage, which fails to shed light on the quality of prescribing. Appropriate antibiotic prescribing entails much more than just not starting; it includes the correct selection of antibiotics, the right dose, the duration of therapy, whether the reason for prescribing is described, the results of the target microbiological test, and the assessment of whether the antibiotic can be switched from intravenous to oral. All these components need to be evaluated to develop focused and effective stewardship and quality improvement initiatives (Schuts et al. 2016; Pulcini et al. 2018). Therefore, this study was conducted to assess prescribing practices and predictors of antibiotic prescribing among in-hospital children with respiratory infections, identify deviations from pediatric antibiotic guidelines, and evaluate patient outcomes.

Methods

Study design and setting

This was a hospital-based cross-sectional observational study conducted among hospitalized children with RTIs at Baghdad Medical City, Baghdad, Iraq. This hospital is an important teaching facility in the city, offering specialized pediatric services to patients from Baghdad and the surrounding governorates. The data were collected from pediatric inpatient wards between September 2025 and January 2026 as part of routine clinical practice, without any modification to treatment decisions. Pediatric patients were recruited using a consecutive sampling technique, in which

all eligible patients admitted to the hospital during the study period were included. The inclusion criteria of pediatric patients were those who were admitted to the pediatric wards with a clinical diagnosis of RTIs and who received antibiotic treatment or were managed without antibiotics during the hospital stay, were between neonates and 14 years of age; and had medical records that were complete and available for antibiotic prescribing and clinical outcomes assessment. However, the exclusion criteria were those with medical records that were either incomplete or missing; transferred to another setting before treatment was completed, or admitted for primary diagnoses that were not RTIs, and who had incidental respiratory symptoms.

Sample size

The sample size was calculated using the single-population proportion method (Charan and Biswas 2013). Assuming an expected proportion of appropriate antibiotic prescribing among pediatric patients of 50%, with a 95% confidence level. In addition, a 7% margin of error was adopted to balance statistical precision with the feasibility constraints of a single tertiary hospital setting and the defined data-collection timeframe. Based on these parameters, the minimum sample size required for the study was 196 patients; however, due to potential data loss and incomplete documentation, the target sample size was set at 200 patients.

Data collection tool

Information was collected uniformly and accurately from the patient's medical and treatment records using a structured, validated form based on prior hospital-based stewardship studies (Di Pietro et al. 2017; Iftikhar et al. 2019; Aricò et al. 2023). The form was divided into three principal sections. Section one encompassed demographic and clinical characteristics (age, gender, type of infection, and length of stay). In addition, details of antibiotic prescribing and the route of administration were provided. Section two contained ten indicators that collectively evaluate the quality of prescribing. They were "guideline adherence," "indication accuracy," "antibiotic choice," "dosing principles," "microbiological investigation," "documentation quality," "opportunities for therapy optimization," "the switch from IV to oral," "duration," and "reassessment". Responses to each indicator were binary as "Yes" for correct practice and "No" for incorrect practice. A score of 1 was given for each correct practice and 0 for an incorrect one. The total prescribing quality for the pediatric patient was calculated by summing the scores of the ten items (ranging from 0 to 10), with higher scores indicating better prescribing performance. This section also collected information on deviations from the guidelines and on prescribing antibiotics based on microbial test results. The last section contained items evaluating clinical outcomes of successful treatment, negative outcomes, readmission, and antibiotic escalation.

The evaluation of appropriate antibiotic prescribing and deviations from guidelines was performed by com-

paring the prescribed treatment with the Pediatric Infectious Diseases Society of America guidelines (Bradley et al. 2011; Yun 2024). In addition to the World Health Organization (WHO) recommendations for childhood pneumonia (World Health Organization 2014) and standard references on pediatric treatment doses. The treatment record of a pediatric patient was considered a deviation when it failed to meet the criteria for drug indication, appropriate selection, dose calculation, and treatment duration outlined in these international guidelines.

Ethical considerations

Approval for the study was obtained from the University of URUK ethical committee for conducting clinical research (Approval No.: URUK/Ph02/2605). Although it was a retrospective collection of information from patients' records during hospitalization, parents or guardians who accompanied their children throughout their hospital stay consented to the use of their children's medical records. In the Iraqi context, parents or guardians usually accompany their children through hospitalization. The researchers informed them of the study's objectives and procedures and obtained consent to review their children's medical charts for data collection. Participation was entirely voluntary, and parents could withdraw their consent without affecting the medical care provided to the pediatric patients. The researchers maintained the confidentiality of the data by using a unique study code for each participant, not collecting identifiable private information, and using the data only for academic purposes.

Statistical analysis

The data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 22. The categorical variables were summarised using frequencies and percentages, and for the continuous variables, means with standard deviations (+ SD) or medians with ranges were provided, as appropriate for the data distribution. Multivariate regression analysis was used to examine the effects of age, gender, type of infection, length of hospital stay, and method of antibiotic administration as independent variables on prescribing quality. Multivariate linear regression coefficients (β) and 95% confidence intervals (CIs) were used to report the findings. The statistical significance level was set at $P < 0.05$.

Results

Demographic and clinical characteristics

A total of 200 pediatric patients with various respiratory infections were included in the study. Their demographic and clinical data are described in Table 1. Slightly more than half of them were females ($n = 105$, 52.5%). The ages of the children ranged from 1 day to 13.5 years (mean =

Table 1. Demographic and clinical characteristics of pediatric patients.

Characteristics	n (%) {n = 200}	
Gender	Female	105 (52.5%)
	Male	95 (47.5%)
Age groups	0–12 months	86 (43.0%)
	1–5 years	53 (26.5%)
	5–12 years	61 (30.5%)
Type of infection	Viral	60 (30.0%)
	Bacterial	120 (60.0%)
	Not documented	20 (10.0%)
Hospital stays in days	1–3	26 (13.0%)
	4–7	19 (9.5%)
	>7	155 (77.5%)
Prescription of antibiotics	Yes	162 (81.0%)
	No	38 (19.0%)

42.2 + 43.3 months; median age = 24 months). The age distribution showed that infants (0–12 months) accounted for the highest proportion of the study cohort ($n = 86$, 43.0%). Of the documented infections, around two-thirds were bacterial ($n = 120$, 60.0%). The number of days spent in the hospital ranged from 1 to 26 (mean = 5.5 + 5.0; median = 4 days). Most children ($n = 155$, 77.5%) had hospital stays lasting more than 7 days. Most patients ($n = 162$, 81.0%) received at least one antibiotic during their hospital stay.

Prescribing behaviors of antibiotics

Out of the 162 pediatric patients prescribed at least one antibiotic, cephalosporins were the most frequently prescribed class ($n = 71$, 43.8%). They were followed by penicillins ($n = 56$, 34.6%). Likewise, glycopeptides (characterized by vancomycin for the most severe or resistant infections) and macrolides (mainly azithromycin) were prescribed in lower amounts ($n = 17$, 10.5%, and $n = 15$, 9.3%, respectively). Aminoglycosides were prescribed even more rarely ($n = 3$, 1.9%). The pattern of cephalosporins and penicillin-class antibiotics indicates widespread use of broad-spectrum antibiotics, as they account for almost 80% of total prescribed antibiotics. The analysis revealed that most pediatric patients received antibiotics via the IV route ($n = 136$, 84.0%), while the remaining ($n = 26$, 16.0%) received them orally. None of the pediatric patients were documented as having received antibiotics by any route other than intravenous or oral administration.

Quality of prescribing practice

There were notable differences in antibiotic prescribing quality across the 10 individual measures, as shown in Table 2. In most cases ($n = 172$, 85.8%), the prescribing was done in accordance with the guidelines. Appropriate antibiotic selection for bacterial infections was documented in more than two-thirds of the cases ($n = 136$, 68.0%). Antibiotics were prescribed for viral infections in 59 cases (29.5%) among the total study population ($n = 200$). Con-

Table 2. Quality indicators of antibiotic prescribing practice.

Practice	n (%) {N = 200}	
	Yes	No
1. Was the antibiotic prescribed according to guidelines?	172 (85.8%)	28 (14.2%)
2. For bacterial infections, was the antibiotic choice appropriate?	136 (68.0%)	64 (32.0%)
3. For viral infections, was an unnecessary antibiotic prescribed?	59 (29.5%)	141 (70.5%)
4. Was the child's weight documented and used for dosing?	55 (27.3%)	145 (72.7%)
5. Was the duration of antibiotic therapy appropriate?	158 (79.1%)	42 (20.9%)
6. Was microbiological testing performed when indicated?	14 (7.1%)	186 (92.9%)
7. Was therapy reviewed within 48–72 hours of initiation?	164 (82.0%)	36 (18.0%)
8. Was the route of antibiotic administration appropriate for the clinical condition?	159 (79.4%)	41 (20.6%)
9. Was the indication for antibiotic therapy clearly documented?	128 (63.8%)	72 (36.2%)
10. Was the IV-to-oral switch performed when clinically appropriate?	178 (89.0%)	22 (11.0%)
Total score	Mean = 6.12 (\pm 1.24), Median = 6	

sidering only patients diagnosed with viral infections ($n = 60$), the 59 cases represent 98.3%. Overall, the key areas of pediatric dosing and stewardship practices showed notable breadth in performance. In only 55 cases (27.3%), prescriptions included calculated weights and doses. In most cases ($n = 158$, 79.1%), the patients followed the recommended treatment duration. Microbiological testing was performed less frequently ($n = 14$, 7.1%). However, in most cases ($n = 164$, 82.0%), a therapy review was performed within 48–72 hours of initiation. The appropriateness of the antibiotic administration route for the clinical condition was found in more than three-quarters of cases ($n = 159$, 79.4%). The indication for antibiotic therapy was documented in more than half of cases ($n = 128$, 63.8%). In addition, switching from IV to oral routes, when clinically warranted, occurred in most cases ($n = 178$, 89.0%). The mean total prescribing quality score across the ten indicators was 6.12 (\pm 1.24), and the median was 6, with scores ranging from 3 to 9, reflecting moderate prescribing quality and indicating potential for improvement in several other stewardship areas.

Multivariable linear regression analysis identified two major factors influencing prescription quality for hospitalized children with respiratory infections, as shown in Table 3. After adjustment for demographic and clinical characteristics, the length of hospital stay was strongly associated with prescription quality, with each additional day resulting in a greater decline in adherence to prescribing standards ($\beta = -0.18$; 95% CI: -0.25 to -0.11 ; $P < 0.001$). Also, IV route use was more likely to be associated with deviation from the guidelines ($\beta = -0.72$; 95% CI: -1.20 to -0.23 ; $P = 0.004$). On the other hand, age, gender, and infection type did not significantly affect prescribing quality performance. Overall, the strongest factors influencing prescription quality were hospital stay and route of treatment, while patient-related factors had far less impact.

Deviation from the guidelines

It was noted that 23 patients' cases (14.19%) (of whom were prescribed antibiotics) deviated from treatment guidelines for various reasons, as shown in Fig. 1. The most frequently noted deviation was overprescribing

($n = 10$, 43%). Followed in order by incorrect duration of treatment ($n = 9$, 37%), incorrectly prescribed dose ($n = 6$, 28%), incorrect choice of antibiotic ($n = 2$, 9%), and the initiation of antibiotic therapy without a clinical indication ($n = 1$, 5%). Of the 14 cases in which microbiological testing was performed, only five (16.7%) required a modification to the initially prescribed antibiotic.

Patient clinical outcome

Pediatric outcomes were analyzed to evaluate the response to the short-term clinical treatment, as shown in Fig. 2. Most cases achieved a successful treatment outcome ($n = 189$, 94.5%). Notably, adverse events occurred in only two cases

Figure 2. Paediatric patients' outcomes.

Table 3. Predictors of prescribing quality of antibiotics for hospitalized children.

Predictors	β coefficient	95% confidence interval	P value
Gender (female)	+0.12	- 0.25 to 0.484	0.52
Age (per 30-day increase)	-0.03	- 0.07 to 0.01	0.14
Length of hospital stay (per 1 day)	-0.18	- 0.25 to - 0.11	<0.001*
Bacterial infection (vs. viral)	-0.21	0.63 to 0.20	0.31
Route (IV vs. oral)	0.72	- 1.20 to - 0.23	0.004*

* Multivariate linear regression analysis, $P < 0.05$.

(1.0%). A few patients ($n = 7$, 3.5%) were readmitted within 7–14 days for the same respiratory infections, interpreted as either early relapse or inadequate initial response. Antibiotic escalation (defined as the need to switch to a broader-spectrum antibiotic or intensify the initial empirical treatment) was noted in more than three-quarters of cases ($n = 177$, 88.5%), reflecting frequent changes to the initial treatment during hospitalization, with almost no microbiological testing. Whereas 23 cases (11.5%) did not require escalation.

Discussion

The study represents the first hospital-based assessment of antibiotic prescription patterns for pediatric respiratory infections in Iraq. While other local studies have focused on antibiotic availability and resistance patterns, this study provides essential baseline data on antibiotic prescribing patterns in pediatric wards. It highlights key areas that should guide future antimicrobial stewardship programs and national policy initiatives. Notably, the high prescription rate of penicillins and cephalosporins suggests broad-spectrum beta-lactam antibiotic use for pediatric respiratory tract infections, often without microbiological confirmation. Similar prescribing patterns have been noted, in which empirical broad-spectrum therapy is chosen due to diagnostic imprecision or concern about the severity of the illness (Di Pietro et al. 2017; Iftikhar et al. 2019; Donà et al. 2020). These antibiotics are effective against various bacterial infections, but their widespread use raises concerns about the risk of superinfection and the potential for antibiotic resistance. The less frequent prescribing of glycopeptides, macrolides, and aminoglycosides may indicate that they are reserved for specific indications or suspected drug-related toxicity. Furthermore, the study observed reliance on IV antibiotics. While this is consistent with the management of children with moderate-to-severe respiratory illness, prolonged IV therapy may increase the risk of longer hospital stays and more catheter-associated complications, while oral therapy is often effective (Donà et al. 2019).

Prescribing quality was adequate, with appropriate antibiotic selection and adherence to guidelines. However, there were deficiencies in some prescribing domains, particularly in the use of antibiotics for viral infections, in dose calculations based on child weight, and in microbiological testing. The use of antibiotics for viral respiratory infections highlights behavioral factors contributing to overprescribing. This problem has been noted in previous literature and at-

tributed to a lack of clear distinction between viral and bacterial infections, potential clinical deterioration, and expectations from the child's caregivers (Hersh et al. 2013; Havers et al. 2018). The lack of weight-based dosing calculations raises a major concern, given that pediatric dosing mistakes remain one of the most significant contributors to drug-related harm to children. Inadequate dosing may lead to both treatment failure and toxicity, underscoring the urgent need for standardized prescribing tools and pharmacist-checking systems (AlAzmi et al. 2019). Another deficiency in prescribing quality was the use of antibiotics for pediatric patients, even in the absence of microbiological data. A low rate of microbiological confirmation is often documented in the literature, especially in resource-constrained environments (O'Brien and PERCH Study Group 2019; Khadse et al. 2023). This indicated that, once antibiotics were administered, clinicians reviewed therapy based on clinical response rather than on the absence of a definitive diagnosis.

In the regression model, hospital length of stay and IV antibiotic use were associated with the lowest antibiotic prescribing quality scores; other demographic variables were not. This means that prescribing quality is affected by institutional rather than patient issues. These same factors have been documented previously, with prolonged hospital stays associated with repeated antibiotic changes, escalated therapy, and deviations from recommended guidelines (Donà et al. 2020). IV therapy is often considered a stewardship concern because it leads to longer hospital stays and increased costs to the whole system (Chapman et al. 2019). This emphasizes the need for detailed guidelines for the transition from IV to oral antibiotics, as well as for clinicians' and pharmacists' stewardship. Most importantly, the lack of correlations with age, gender, and infection type highlights that the success of stewardship is more a function of hospital policy, the presence of audit-and-feedback, and multidisciplinary oversight than of clinician experience. Thus, in this context, improving prescribing will likely require more extensive system-level changes than merely addressing individual prescribers or specific patients.

Deviation from the guidelines, characterized mostly by overprescribing and incorrect treatment duration, was noted in some cases. This indicates that inadequate antimicrobial management remains a problem in pediatric respiratory infections. Pediatric studies conducted in hospitals have documented similar issues stemming from diagnostic uncertainty and fear of disease worsening, leading to unnecessarily prolonged antibiotic treatment (Hersh et al. 2013; Bassetti et al. 2019). Another finding of this study revealed

limited modification of therapy in response to microbial test results. This demonstrates a common barrier to effective stewardship in pediatric settings and inadequate use of diagnostic information to guide more targeted treatment.

Despite prescribing variations, a positive clinical outcome with successful treatment and a low incidence of adverse drug reactions and readmissions was noted. The short-term clinical improvement does not reflect optimal use of the prescribed antibiotics and may even mask inappropriate prescribing, a phenomenon also reported in pediatric stewardship assessments (Schuts et al. 2016). Furthermore, the high rate of antibiotic escalation observed in this study does not necessarily indicate treatment failure; rather, it may reflect a pattern of cautious prescribing and frequent modification of initial therapy. Therefore, the positive clinical success achieved by this study should not be considered evidence of appropriate prescribing. Many respiratory tract infections in children, particularly viral infections, are self-limiting and will resolve without antibiotic therapy. Therefore, the observed clinical outcomes may reflect the nature of the disease rather than the therapeutic benefit of broad-spectrum antibiotics. Although escalation of antibiotic therapy may be clinically reasonable, modification of treatment in the absence of microbiological culture results raises concerns about unnecessary exposure to broad-spectrum antibiotics, the possibility of antimicrobial resistance, and increased healthcare costs (Picca et al. 2023; Puzz et al. 2023). This highlighted the need to enhance diagnostic stewardship and improve the timeliness of therapy reassessment to optimize the antibiotic selection and reduce unnecessary exposure to broad-spectrum antibiotics.

Study limitations

The data of this study were collected from a single tertiary care hospital, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to other healthcare settings in Iraq. In addition, a possible bias in patient recruitment may arise from the use of consecutive sampling. To minimize this risk, all eligible pediatric patients were included without restrictions during data collection. Moreover, relying on medical records as the sole source may underestimate the findings, as some stewardship activities may have been conducted but not documented. Another limitation of the scoring criteria for stewardship indicators is that they were not previously validated in the Iraqi context. However, they were adapted from previously published prescribing tools used in a pediatric clinical setting. Despite these limitations, the study highlighted an important issue for improving antimicrobial stewardship in hospitalized pediatric patients with respiratory infections.

Conclusion

The quality of prescribing antibiotics for pediatric patients in this study was moderate. Although most prescribing practices aligned with the guidelines, gaps

remained in diagnostic stewardship, weight-based dosing, the inappropriate use of antibiotics for viral infections, and the limited documentation of microbiological testing. Prescribing quality was affected by institutional factors, such as long hospital stays and IV administration routes. Deviations from the guidelines were characterized mostly by overprescribing antibiotics and incorrect dosing intervals. Although favorable clinical outcomes were achieved, they did not reflect appropriate antibiotic prescribing, given the self-limiting nature of many respiratory tract infections. Findings of this study highlight the need for enhancing the hospital's antimicrobial stewardship programs. More consistent prescribing, regular clinical audits with feedback, and stronger clinical pharmacy stewardship would most likely improve the appropriateness of antibiotic prescribing.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

Funding

The study was conducted without funding support from any organization or institute.

Author contributions

All authors have contributed equally.

Author ORCIDs

Inas Rifaat Ibrahim <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3980-3076>

Yahya G. Karwi <https://orcid.org/0009-0004-9433-8869>

Hamoudi Aliwi Mousah <https://orcid.org/0009-0008-1659-1139>

Ibrahim A. Majeed <https://orcid.org/0009-0005-8489-5642>

Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

References

- AlAzmi A, Ahmed O, Alhamdan H, AlGarni H, Elzain RM, AlThubaiti RS, Aseeri M, Al Shaikh A (2019) Epidemiology of preventable drug-related problems among hospitalized children at KAMC-Jeddah. *Drug, Healthcare and Patient Safety* 11: 95–103. <https://doi.org/10.2147/DHPS.S220081>
- Aricò MO, Valletta E, Caselli D (2023) Appropriate use of antibiotics and principles of antimicrobial stewardship in children. *Children* 10(4): 740. <https://doi.org/10.3390/children10040740>
- Bassetti M, Giacobbe DR, Vena A, Brink A (2019) Challenges and research priorities to progress the impact of antimicrobial stewardship. *Drugs in Context* 8: 212600. <https://doi.org/10.7573/dic.212600>
- Bradley JS, Byington CL, Shah SS, Alverson B, Carter ER, Harrison C, Kaplan S, Mace S, McCracken G, Moore M, Peter S, Stockwell J, Swanson J (2011) The management of community-acquired pneumonia in infants and children older than 3 months of age. *Clinical Infectious Diseases* 53(7): e25–e76. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cid/cir531>
- Chapman ALN, Patel S, Horner C, Green H, Guleri A, Hedderwick S, Snape S, Statham J, Wilson E, Gilchrist M, Seaton R (2019) Updated good practice recommendations for outpatient parenteral antimicrobial therapy in adults and children in the UK. *JAC-Antimicrobial Resistance* 1(2): dlz026. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jacamr/dlz026>
- Charan J, Biswas T (2013) How to calculate sample size for different study designs in medical research. *Indian Journal of Psychological Medicine* 35(2): 121–126. <https://doi.org/10.4103/0253-7176.116232>
- Di Pietro P, Della Casa Alberighi O, Silvestri M, Caruso D, Esposito S (2017) Monitoring adherence to guidelines of antibiotic use in pediatric pneumonia: The MAREA study. *Italian Journal of Pediatrics* 43: 113. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13052-017-0432-2>
- Donà D, Barbieri E, Daverio M, Lundin R, Giaquinto C, Zaoutis T, Sharland M (2020) Implementation and impact of pediatric antimicrobial stewardship programs: A systematic scoping review. *Antimicrobial Resistance and Infection Control* 9: 3. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13756-019-0659-3>
- Donà D, Luise D, La Pergola E, Da Dalt M, Giaquinto C (2020) Effects of antimicrobial stewardship intervention on pediatric antibiotic prescribing. *European Journal of Pediatrics* 179: 201–210.
- Donà D, Luise D, La Pergola E, Montemezzo G, Frigo A, Lundin R, Zaoutis T, Gamba P, Giaquinto C (2019) Effects of an antimicrobial stewardship intervention on perioperative antibiotic prophylaxis in pediatrics. *Antimicrobial Resistance and Infection Control* 8: 13. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13756-019-0464-z>
- Gerber JS, Prasad PA, Localio AR, Fiks AG, Grundmeier RW, Bell LM, Waserman RC, Keren R, Zaoutis TE (2013) Effect of an outpatient antimicrobial stewardship intervention on broad-spectrum antibiotic prescribing. *JAMA* 309(22): 2345–2352. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2013.6287>
- Havers FP, Blanton L, Jain S, Reed C, Lindstrom RS, McSpadden EK, Hicks LA (2018) Outpatient antibiotic prescribing for acute respiratory infections during influenza seasons. *Clinical Infectious Diseases* 67(1): 18–25.
- Hersh AL, Jackson MA, Hicks MM (2013) Principles of judicious antibiotic prescribing for pediatric upper respiratory tract infections. *Pediatrics* 132(6): 1146–1154. <https://doi.org/10.1542/peds.2013-3260>
- Iftikhar S, Sarwar MR, Saqib A, Sarfraz M, Shoaib QU (2019) Antibiotic prescribing practices and errors among hospitalised pediatric patients suffering from acute respiratory tract infections: A multi-center cross-sectional study in Pakistan. *Medicina* 55(2): 44. <https://doi.org/10.3390/medicina55020044>
- Khadse SN, Ugemuge S, Singh C (2023) Impact of antimicrobial stewardship on reducing antimicrobial resistance. *Cureus* 15(12): e49935. <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.49935>
- Nair H, Simões EAF, Rudan I, Gessner PS, Campbell DRA, Boschi-Pinto C, Cherian T, Bhutta ZA, Campbell H (2013) Global and regional burden of hospital admissions for severe acute lower respiratory infections in young children in 2010: A systematic analysis. *The Lancet* 381(9875): 1380–1390. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(12\)61901-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(12)61901-1)
- Nedved A, Lee BR, Hamner M, Wirtz A, Burns A, El Feghaly RE (2023) Impact of an antibiotic stewardship program on antibiotic choice, dosing, and duration in pediatric urgent cares. *American Journal of Infection Control* 51(5): 520–526. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajic.2022.07.027>
- O'Brien KL, PERCH Study Group (2019) Causes of severe pneumonia requiring hospital admission in children without HIV infection from Africa and Asia. *The Lancet* 394(10200): 757–779. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(19\)30721-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(19)30721-4)
- Picca M, Chiotos K, Gerber JS (2023) Leading reasons for antibiotic prescriptions in pediatric respiratory infections and opportunities for antimicrobial stewardship. *Antibiotics* 12(10): 1504. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13052-023-01533-5>
- Puzz L, Chiotos K, Tamma PD, Cosgrove SE, Gerber JS (2023) Evaluation of an antimicrobial stewardship intervention on antibiotic prescribing in pediatric community-acquired pneumonia. *Antibiotics* 12(3): 463. <https://doi.org/10.3390/antibiotics12040780>
- Pulcini C, Tacconelli E, Tumbarello M, De Rosa FGM (2018) Role of diagnostics in antimicrobial stewardship. *Clinical Microbiology and Infection* 24(6): 561–563.
- Schuts EC, Hulscher MEJL, Mouton JW, Verduin CM, Stuart J, Overdiek HWPM, Linden PD, Natsch S, Hertogh CMPM, Wolfs TFW, Schouten J, Kullberg BJ, Prins JM (2016) Current evidence on hospital antimicrobial stewardship objectives. *The Lancet Infectious Diseases* 16(7): 847–856. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1473-3099\(16\)00065-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1473-3099(16)00065-7)
- GBD 2016 Lower Respiratory Infections Collaborators (2018) Estimates of the global, regional, and national morbidity, mortality, and aetiologies of lower respiratory infections in 195 countries, 1990–2016: A systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2016. *The Lancet Infectious Diseases* 18(11): 1191–1210. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1473-3099\(18\)30310-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1473-3099(18)30310-4)
- World Health Organization (2014) Revised WHO classification and treatment of pneumonia in children at health facilities: Evidence summaries. World Health Organization, Geneva. <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789241507813>
- World Health Organization (2024) Pneumonia. Fact sheet. <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/pneumonia>
- Yun KW (2024) Community-acquired pneumonia in children: Updated perspectives on its etiology, diagnosis, and treatment. *Clinical and Experimental Pediatrics* 67: 80–89. <https://doi.org/10.3345/cep.2022.01452>